

EFFECT OF MICRO-LEARNING INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY ON STUDENT INTEREST AND GENDER IN BIOLOGY IN AKPABUYO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of a micro-learning instructional strategy on students' interest and gender differences in biology in Akpabuyo Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental research design. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The sample comprised 160 Senior Secondary II (SSII) students drawn from a population of 2,700 students in the study area. The research instruments included a researcher-developed Biology Achievement Test (BAT) and a Biology Interest Questionnaire (BIQ). To ensure validity, the instruments were subjected to expert review for face and content validation by specialists in science education and measurement and evaluation, leading to necessary modifications before administration. The reliability of the BAT was established using the Kuder-Richardson formula (KR-20), yielding a coefficient of 0.85, while the interest questionnaire had a Cronbach's alpha reliability index of 0.74, indicating acceptable internal consistency. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation, and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The results revealed that students' interest in the concept taught was significantly higher among those exposed to the micro-learning instructional strategy. However, gender had no statistically significant effect on students' academic achievement. Based on these findings, it was recommended that biology and other science teachers integrate micro-learning strategies into classroom instruction to enhance students' interest, motivation, and overall academic performance in science concepts.

Keywords: *Micro-Learning, Conventional Strategy, Gender, Interest*

Introduction

Biology, as a branch of science, is fundamentally concerned with the study of living organisms and their interactions with one another and with their environment. It encompasses a wide range of concepts, including the structure and function of living systems, growth and development, heredity and evolution, ecology, and the mechanisms that sustain life. Within the context of science education, biology plays a pivotal role because it equips learners with essential knowledge and skills for understanding life processes, environmental sustainability, health-related issues, and the interdependence of living and non-living components of the ecosystem.

Consequently, biology is not only central to scientific literacy but also indispensable for informed decision-making in everyday life.

In an ideal instructional context, biology teaching is expected to be engaging, interactive, and learner-centered, fostering students' curiosity, critical thinking, and sustained interest in scientific inquiry. However, this ideal is often not realized in many educational settings, where students' interest and engagement in biology have continued to decline. One of the major factors contributing to this trend is the persistent use of conventional teacher-centered instructional approaches. Traditional lecture-based methods

often involve the transmission of large volumes of abstract and content-heavy information within limited classroom time. This mode of delivery positions students as passive recipients of knowledge rather than active participants in the learning process. As a result, learners may experience cognitive overload, which hinders meaningful understanding and retention of biological concepts, ultimately leading to the perception of biology as abstract, difficult, and uninteresting. The consequences of this persistent problem are far-reaching. Continued low interest in biology can result in poor academic achievement, reduced enrollment in science-related disciplines, and a decline in students pursuing careers in science, health, and technology fields. At a broader level, this may negatively impact societal development, particularly in areas such as healthcare, environmental sustainability, and biotechnology, which depend heavily on biological knowledge (Anari et al., 2025). These challenges underscore the urgent need for innovative instructional strategies that can rekindle students' interest and improve their engagement in biology learning.

In response to these concerns, the rapid advancement of digital technologies and the increasing emphasis on learner-centered pedagogies have encouraged educators to explore more effective teaching approaches (Neji et al., 2025). One such approach is micro-learning, a pedagogical strategy that presents instructional content in short, focused, and easily digestible segments. Micro-learning emphasizes concise learning materials, interactive multimedia resources, and immediate feedback, all of which are designed to enhance students' engagement and understanding of subject matter (Silver et al., 2025). By breaking down complex biological concepts into manageable units, micro-learning facilitates quick comprehension and

improves retention, making learning more accessible and meaningful.

The effectiveness of micro-learning has been widely supported in contemporary educational research. For instance, Pitaloka (2025) found that students exposed to video-based micro-learning modules demonstrated significantly higher academic achievement and motivation compared to those taught using conventional lecture methods. Similarly, Mohammed et al. (2018) reported that micro-learning enhances students' learning ability by presenting information in small, manageable units that promote continuous learning and sustained engagement. These findings are consistent with other studies (Abidin, 2025; Salleh et al., 2022; Fidan, 2023; Sankaranarayanan et al., 2023), which revealed that micro-learning significantly improves students' interest, engagement, and overall learning outcomes.

Furthermore, research on digital learning environments indicates that micro-learning supports learner autonomy and flexibility by allowing students to access instructional materials anytime and anywhere (Rof et al., 2024). This flexibility accommodates diverse learning styles and enables learners to revisit content at their own pace, thereby enhancing understanding and retention. The provision of immediate feedback in micro-learning environments also allows students to identify and correct misconceptions promptly, further strengthening learning outcomes. The theoretical foundations of micro-learning are rooted in constructivism and self-determination theory. Constructivist theory by Piaget (1977) posits that learners actively construct knowledge through interaction and experience, while self-determination theory by Deci and Ryan (2000) emphasizes the roles of autonomy, competence, and intrinsic motivation in effective learning.

Micro-learning aligns with these perspectives by promoting active participation, reducing cognitive load, and fostering a sense of control over the learning process. These attributes make it particularly suitable for teaching complex and conceptually demanding subjects such as biology.

In addition to instructional strategies, gender has been widely examined as a variable influencing students' learning outcomes in science education. Some studies suggest that differences in learning preferences, confidence levels, and classroom participation may lead to variations in academic achievement between male and female students. However, learner-centered approaches such as micro-learning may help reduce these disparities by providing equal opportunities for engagement and individualized learning experiences. Empirical evidence on gender differences remains mixed. While some studies (e.g., Prihatin et al., 2025; Mohammed, 2023; McNeill & Fitch, 2023) reported no significant gender differences in students' academic achievement, others (e.g., Almasri, 2022) found significant variations between male and female students in science performance.

Despite the growing body of literature supporting the effectiveness of micro-learning, there remains a noticeable gap in research regarding its influence on students' interest in biology, particularly with respect to gender differences in secondary school contexts. Most existing studies have focused on academic achievement and motivation, with less attention given to students' interest as a critical affective variable in learning. Addressing this gap is essential, as interest plays a central role in shaping students' engagement, persistence, and overall learning outcomes. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the effect of micro-learning instructional strategy on students' interest in biology and to determine whether gender moderates this effect. By doing so, the study contributes to the growing body of

knowledge on innovative instructional strategies and provides empirical evidence to inform teaching practices aimed at improving students' interest and engagement in biology.

Statement of the Problem

An effective biology classroom should be engaging and learner-centered, fostering curiosity about living systems. Students must actively participate in learning activities and achieve a meaningful understanding of biological concepts relevant to their lives and careers. This environment promotes scientific literacy, critical thinking, and a positive attitude toward science. However, many secondary schools fail to achieve this ideal, as students often exhibit low interest in biology. A significant factor is the reliance on traditional teacher-centered methods, particularly lectures, which treat students as passive recipients of information. This approach tends to present biology as abstract and challenging, diminishing enthusiasm for learning. Scholars indicate that such strategies contribute to declining interest in science since they do not effectively involve students in knowledge construction (Amaefuna & Ezeliora, 2021).

Additionally, traditional teaching methods clash with the learning preferences of today's students, who are increasingly accustomed to digital technologies and interactive learning. The lack of innovative, technology-supported instructional strategies further leads to disengagement and inadequate academic performance in biology. If these issues persist, consequences may include poor academic outcomes, decreased enrollment in science courses, and fewer students pursuing careers in science, technology, and healthcare. This trend could negatively impact national development in fields reliant on scientific knowledge, such as healthcare and environmental management. To address these challenges, it is critical to explore innovative instructional strategies that

enhance student interest and engagement in biology. Micro-learning presents a promising approach, delivering content in concise, interactive formats that align with learners' attention spans and digital preferences. While prior studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in various educational contexts, empirical evidence regarding its impact on student interest in biology, specifically concerning gender differences in secondary settings, remains limited, highlighting the need for further investigation.

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What are the mean interest scores of students taught biology using a micro-learning adaptive strategy and those taught with a conventional strategy?
2. What is the mean difference in the achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using a micro-learning adaptive strategy and those taught with a conventional strategy?

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught biology using a micro-learning adaptive strategy and those taught with a conventional strategy.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using a micro-learning adaptive strategy and those taught with a conventional strategy.

Research Methods

The study adopted a quasi-experimental pretest–posttest control group design to investigate the effect of a micro-learning instructional strategy on students' interest in biology. This design was considered appropriate because it allows for the comparison of outcomes between an experimental group and a control group while controlling for initial group differences through the use of pretest scores. The experimental group was exposed to the micro-learning instructional strategy, whereas the control group received instruction using the conventional lecture method.

The population of the study comprised 2,700 Senior Secondary School II (SS II) biology students in public secondary schools within the study area. A sample of 160 students was selected using a multistage sampling procedure. At the first stage, two public secondary schools were selected using purposive sampling based on criteria such as similarity in academic standards, availability of qualified biology teachers, and comparable learning environments. This ensured equivalence and reduced extraneous variability. At the second stage, intact classes were selected from each school using cluster sampling, since random assignment of individual students was not feasible in a school setting. One intact class from each school was then randomly assigned to either the experimental or control group using simple random sampling (e.g., balloting technique). The sample included both male and female students, thereby allowing for the examination of gender differences.

Two instruments were used to collect data: The Biology Interest Questionnaire (BIQ) and the Biology Achievement Test (BAT). The BIQ was designed to measure students' interest in biology and consisted of 10 items on a four-

point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The BAT consisted of 20 multiple-choice questions covering topics such as ecology, animal nutrition, and soil science, and was used to assess students' understanding of the concepts taught during the instructional period.

The instruments were subjected to face and content validation by experts in biology education and educational measurement and evaluation from the University of Calabar. The experts examined the items for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study objectives, and their suggestions were incorporated into the final versions of the instruments. A pilot study was conducted using 50 SS II students from schools outside the study sample to establish the reliability of the instruments. The Kuder–Richardson (KR-20) formula was used to estimate the reliability of the BAT, yielding a coefficient of 0.85, while the Cronbach's alpha method was used for the BIQ, producing a reliability coefficient of 0.74. These values indicated that the instruments were sufficiently reliable for the study.

The experimental procedure lasted for four weeks. The experimental group was taught using micro-learning instructional modules, which included short video lessons, concise explanatory notes, and interactive quizzes. Each lesson was delivered in brief, focused segments targeting specific biological concepts to enhance comprehension and retention. In contrast, the control group was taught the same content using the conventional lecture method.

The researcher, with the assistance of biology teachers in the selected schools, administered the instruments. Pretests were conducted before the commencement of the instructional treatment to establish baseline equivalence between the groups, while posttests were

administered at the end of the four-week instructional period.

Data coding followed standard quantitative research procedures. For the Biology Achievement Test, each correct response was scored as 1 point, while incorrect responses were scored as 0. For the Biology Interest Questionnaire, responses were scored as follows: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1) for positively worded items, with reverse scoring applied to negatively worded items. Additional coding included gender (Male = 1, Female = 2) and group classification (Control = 1, Experimental = 2). All data were entered into statistical software, followed by data cleaning, verification, and scoring prior to analysis.

Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance, with pretest scores used as covariates to control for initial group differences. The decision rule for hypothesis testing was that the null hypothesis would be rejected if the calculated p-value was less than or equal to 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$), indicating a statistically significant effect. Conversely, the null hypothesis would be retained if the p-value was greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), indicating that the effect was not statistically significant.

Results

Research Question One: What are the mean interest scores of students taught biology using a micro-learning adaptive strategy and those taught with a conventional strategy?

Table 1: Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation of students’ pre-interest and post-interest scores classified by treatment groups

Treatment Groups	N	Pre-interest		Post-interest		Mean Gain Score
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Conventional strategy	100	11.48	1.99	26.59	2.38	15.11
Micro-learning strategy	60	16.71	18.21	33.68	3.15	16.97

Table 1 shows the pre- and post-interest mean scores and standard deviations for students taught using micro-learning and conventional strategies. The pre- and post-interest mean gain scores were 15.11 and 16.97 for the conventional and micro-learning groups, respectively. This indicated that students in the micro-learning group had a larger mean gain score difference than those in the conventional group. However, the pre-interest and post-interest mean scores of 11.48 and 26.67 for those in the conventional strategy, and 16.71 and 33.68 for students in the micro-learning strategy, indicate that both groups had post-interest scores higher than their pre-interest

scores, implying that both groups benefited from the treatment provided. The post-interest mean score of those in the experimental group was observed to be higher than that of the control. Whether the observed differences in the mean scores of the two groups were statistically significant is assessed by the results of hypothesis testing presented in Table 2.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught biology using a micro-learning adaptive strategy and those taught with a conventional strategy.

Table 2: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the students’ post-interest scores classified by treatment groups with pre-interest scores as covariate

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision at p<.05 alpha
Corrected Model	1901.954 ^a	2	950.977	131.193	.000	S
Intercept	56071.709	1	56071.709	7735.416	.000	S
Pre-interest	15.127	1	15.127	2.087	.151	NS
Treatment	1868.099	1	1868.099	257.715	.000	S
Error	1138.046	157	7.249			
Total	139930.000	160				
Corrected Total	3040.000	159				

a. R Squared = .626 (Adjusted R Squared = .621)

b. Computed using alpha = .05

In Table 2, the calculated F-ratio for the effect of instructional strategies (df 1, 157) is 7.249, and the corresponding alpha level is 0.000. This level of significance is lower than the .05 threshold used to make the decision, indicating a significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught using the micro-learning instructional strategy compared with

the conventional strategy. With this observation, null hypothesis 1 was rejected.

Research Question Two: What is the mean difference in the achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using a micro-learning adaptive strategy and those taught with a conventional strategy?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of students’ pre-test and post-test scores classified by treatment groups and gender

Descriptive Statistics					
Dependent Variable: POSTTEST					
TREATMENT	GENDER	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	
Conventional	MALE	49.6222	4.25488	45	
	FEMALE	48.3455	2.88815	55	
	Total	48.9200	3.60606	100	
Micro-learning	MALE	63.8571	3.52467	28	
	FEMALE	61.8125	5.23288	32	
	Total	62.7667	4.59685	60	

Table 3 shows the post-test mean scores and standard deviations for male and female students taught using micro-learning and Conventional strategies. The mean scores for male students in the conventional group are 49.62 and 63.85 in the micro-learning group, while the mean scores for female students in the conventional group are 48.34 and 61.81 in the micro-learning group. This observation shows that both male and female students in the micro-learning group performed better than their male and female counterparts in the

conventional group. Whether the differences in mean scores between the two groups by gender were statistically significant was determined by testing hypothesis two using the results in Table 4

Hypothesis two: 2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using a micro-learning adaptive strategy and those taught with a conventional strategy

Table 4. Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of students’ post-test scores classified by treatment groups, and gender, with pre-test scores as covariate

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision at p<.05 alpha
Pretest	7.881	1	7.881	.504	.479	NS
Treatment	6103.079	1	6103.079	390.345	.000	S
Gender	106.411	1	106.411	6.806	.010	NS
Treatment * Gender	5.493	1	5.493	.351	.554	NS

Error	2423.437	155	15.635
Total	478230.000	160	
Corrected Total	9723.975	159	

- a. a. R Squared = .751 (Adjusted R Squared = .744)
- b. Computed using alpha = .05

In Table 4, the calculated F-ratio for the interaction effects of treatment, gender, and school location on Chemistry students' academic achievement at df 1, 155 is 15.635. In contrast, its corresponding calculated level of significance is 0.554 (alpha). This level of significance is greater than .05 in which the decision is based, indicating that there were no significant effects of treatment and gender on biology achievement. With this observation, null hypothesis 4 was upheld. With respect to research question 4, the observations indicate that the two strategies had the same effects across all gender levels, and that gender had the same effect across all treatment levels.

Discussions of Findings

The findings concerning the effect of micro-learning, conventional strategies and student's interest in biology showed that there was statistically significant difference in the level of the student's interest in biology using micro-learning and conventional instructional strategies in favour of those in micro-learning group at a significant level of .000 with a post interest mean score of 33.68 which is higher than that of the conventional group with a post mean score of 26.59, This suggest that after the treatment, the experimental group ended with a higher mean score when compared to the conventional group, the micro-learning group also had a higher mean gain of 16.97 compared to that of the conventional group with a mean gain of 15.11.This is attributed to the strategy being student-centred which engages students in activities that excite their cognitive abilities and promote deep learning, making students active participants in the construction of knowledge while the teacher takes the role of a

facilitator of instruction. This agrees with the findings of Abidin (2025), Salleh et al., (2022), Fidan (2023), and Sankaranarayanan et al.,(2023), who reported on the impact of micro-learning instructional strategy in increasing students' interest in their studies when compared to conventional strategy.

On the effect of the instructional strategies on gender and students' achievement, the findings showed there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of students on the concepts taught using micro-learning and the conventional strategy, with a significant level of .554. This observation indicates that gender is not a significant determinant of students' academic outcomes and that boys and girls have reached parity in their achievement in biology and science. This aligns with the findings of (Prihatin et al.,2025, Anari et al.,2025; Mohammed, 2023, McNeill, & Fitch, 2023), but contradicts that of Almasri, (2022) The findings from the study also indicated that both male and female benefited from the instructional strategies used, though male and female in the micro-learning group had a higher post mean score than their counter part in the conventional group, however this mean difference was not statistically significant.

Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of micro-learning on students' interest in Biology, as well as the influence of gender. Results showed that micro-learning significantly increased students' interest compared to conventional teaching methods, enhancing engagement and participation. Additionally, gender did not affect students' interest, with

both male and female students responding similarly to the approach. This suggests that micro-learning is effective for all learners. The study concludes that educators should incorporate micro-learning strategies in science instruction to boost engagement and foster sustained interest in the subject.

Recommendation

1. Since the study found no significant gender difference in students' interest, teachers should continue to implement instructional strategies such as micro-learning that promote equal participation and learning opportunities for both male and female students.
2. Future researchers should conduct similar studies in other science subjects, such as chemistry and physics, as well as in different educational levels and geographical locations, to further validate the effectiveness of micro-learning instructional strategies in enhancing students' interest and academic achievement

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